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Educational Facilities Availability And Utilization As Correlates Of Secondary School Students' Academic Performance In Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined 'Educational facilities availability and utilization as correlates of secondary schools students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria'. Two (2) objectives, two (2) research questions and two (2) corresponding null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study was anchored on resource dependence theory. The study adopted a correlational research design with a population of 8452 teachers in 268 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State out of which a sample of 382 teachers representing 4.51% was drawn using Taro Yamane minimum sample formula. The study used three different sets of instruments titled: 'Educational Facilities Availability Checklist' (EFAC) and Questionnaire titled: 'Utilization of Educational Facilities Questionnaire' (UEFQ) and 'Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire' (SAPQ). The three instruments were scored on a four points scale and validated by the researcher's supervisors and one expert in the field of Measurement and Evaluation of the Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling, University of Port Harcourt. The reliability coefficient obtained for EFAC was 0.93 while UEFQ and SAPQ were 0.89 and 0.86 respectively. Simple regression was used to answer research questions 1-2. T-test associated with simple regression were used to test the null hypotheses 1-2 at 0.05 levels of significance. The findings of the study showed that to a very high extent, availability and utilization of classroom instructional facilities and library facilities, correlate with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommended amongst others that, government should create enabling policies and incentives that encourage private sector investment in education infrastructure, ensuring sustainable support for instructional facility development and effective monitoring mechanisms to guarantee quality and usage.

Keywords: Academic performance, Educational facilities,

INTRODUCTION

Education is a fundamental component of human development and socio-economic advancement. In Nigeria, education is a key tool for empowering the youth and shaping the future of the nation. The

importance of secondary education, particularly in secondary schools, cannot be overstated as it serves as a foundation for higher education and prepares students for the workforce. Secondary schools, therefore, play a pivotal role in determining the future educational and economic success of students. The academic performance of secondary school students is influenced by a wide range of factors. These include socio-economic conditions teacher quality, curriculum, and most importantly, the availability and utilization of educational facilities within schools (Abdulhakeem, 2020). Educational facilities, such as classrooms, libraries, laboratories, and other resources, have been found to significantly affect learning outcomes, the role of these facilities become even more important in rural and semi-urban areas, where resources are often limited and where students may have fewer opportunities to access quality learning materials.

The term “academic performance of students” refers to how well they achieve educational goals, typically measured through grades, test scores, and other assessments. This performance is influenced by various factors, including cognitive abilities, socio-economic status, access to educational resources, teacher effectiveness, and the home environment. In secondary schools, academic performance is an important indicator of students’ readiness for higher education and the workforce (Akinlabi and Oladipo, 2021). This author states that the most direct and commonly used indicators of academic performance in secondary schools are students’ grades in various subjects and their performance on standardized tests. High marks typically reflect mastery of the curriculum, while low marks may suggest challenges in understanding the material or lack of engagement. If students’ academic performance is so desired, there is need for educational facilities availability and utilization

Educational facilities refer to the physical spaces and resources designed to support the teaching and learning process. These facilities include schools, libraries, laboratories, sports areas, and other infrastructures like auditoriums, computer rooms, and cafeterias that help create an environment conducive to education. Educational facilities are essential for ensuring that students have access to the tools and spaces they need to learn effectively. Educational facilities play a critical role in shaping students’ academic performance. Research consistently indicates that the quality and condition of school infrastructures significantly impact learning outcomes. A study by Adeyemo (2021) in Bauchi State, Nigeria, examines the influence of school facilities on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students reveals that, the availability and quality of school facilities directly affect students’ academic performance, schools with better-equipped classrooms, libraries, and laboratories provided environments conducive to learning, leading to improved student outcomes. Similarly, research in Rivers State, Nigeria, highlights that the availability of educational facilities significantly influences students’ academic performance in public senior secondary schools. The study found that school with adequate facilities created conducive learning environments, leading to improved student engagement and achievement.

Conceptually, educational facilities availability refers to the accessibility and provision of resources, infrastructure, and services necessary for supporting education, this includes schools and colleges, classrooms and learning spaces, teaching materials and resources, accessibility, teachers and staff, facilities for extracurricular activities and technology integration (Ademola and Adebayo, 2022). It is crucial for a good education system to have a wide range of these facilities available to ensure that all students have the opportunity to succeed academically. The availability and utilization of adequate school buildings, classrooms, chairs, desks and other facilities as asserts by Amaechinwa (2024) are necessary for the attainment of education objectives. This is corroborated by Adeboyeje, cited in Akinola (2020) through his definition of physical facilities as the essential materials that must be put in place and into consideration for the objectives of the school system to be accomplished. The extent of availability and utilization of these facilities determines the quality of instruction and performance of both teachers and students in the school.

“Availability” as defines by Alabi and Adedeji. (2021), means enabling access to authorized information or resources to those who need them. It is the ability to make information and related physical facilities accessible as needed, when they are needed, and where they are needed. Availability is the capacity of an education system or its authorities to make facilities available, including all the logical and physical

facilities reachable and accessible wherever and whenever they are needed. Availability refers to the accessibility and presence of educational resources, opportunities and services, in essence, availability in education ensures that students have the chance to access and benefit from educational opportunities regardless of their background, location, or socio-economic status.

“Utilization”, according to Ugwuanyi (2023), simply represents the actual patronage of the schools’ facilities, equipment and supplies by the teacher in teaching. Dauda (2021) cited in Ugwuanyi (2023) explains utilization as to make use of available services at the individual’s disposal. It further means that something is equal to or fully sufficient for a specified or implied requirement. It also means how facilities are used to get good results (Okoro, 2016). When facilities are sufficiently available in school, teachers get the satisfaction they need in utilizing them in teaching and learning and their best performances in using the facilities in the classroom is guaranteed. Of all the pre-requisites for effective management of an organization as asserts, the most vital is the human resources that should be accorded with sufficient materials to utilize. Utilization refers to the effective use or application of facilities, strategies, tools, or knowledge to achieve educational goal. In all these contexts, the core idea is about making the best use of available facilities and opportunities to improve education. Proper-utilization helps students achieve academic success and educators-optimize their teaching methods. The availability of school facilities is crucial for providing a conducive learning environment. School facilities include both physical infrastructure and facilities that support teaching, learning, and extra-curricular activities. The key components of educational facilities availability according to Okoro (2016) are; classroom instructional facilities, library facilities, laboratories, recreational facilities, technology facilities, staff rooms and administrative facilities and transportation facilities.

Classroom instructional facilities refer the physical and technological resources available in a classroom that support teaching and learning. The quality and availability of these instructional facilities can significantly impact secondary school students’ academic performances in several ways. This is because, a well-equipped and comfortable classroom environment can increase student engagement. For example, interactive whiteboards and educational technology can make lesson more engaging and interactive, fostering better understanding and retention. Okoro (2016) notes that a positive and well-maintained classroom with good lighting, ventilation, and organized seating can reduce distractions, allowing students to focus better. A conducive learning environment helps improve cognitive performance, leading to higher academic achievement.

Library facilities refer to the resources, services, and physical spaces available in a school or educational institution that support learning, research, and personal development. These facilities are designed to provide students with access to information, books, multimedia, and quiet spaces for study and research. Library facilities are vital for fostering self-directed learning, improving academic performance, and developing critical thinking skills. They provide students with access to a wealth of information, encourage reading habits, and help students with research and study projects. This library is an essential hub for learning, promoting intellectual development and supporting academic success. Dauda (2021) opines that libraries provide students with access to textbooks, research materials, and the internet, all of which can enhance their understanding of subjects and provide supplementary resources beyond classroom instruction. The availability and effective use of library facilities have a significant impact on the academic performance of secondary school students. Libraries support students’ learning, foster independent study, and contributes to improved academic outcomes through better access to resources and guidance.

The study was anchored on Resource Dependence Theory (RDT) propounded by Jeffrey Pfeffer and Gerald R. Salancik in the year 1978. RDT is underpinned by the idea that resources are the key to organizational success and that access and control over resources is a basis of power. Power here means performance and functionality of an organization. Resource Dependence Theory (RDT) identified that the organizations depend on external resources for survival. And these external resources of organizations which are multidimensional like: labour, capital, raw materials affect the behaviour of the organization and including workers output and performance in the organization. Therefore, the procurement of external

facilities is an important tenet of both the strategic and tactical management of any company. Managers' careers thrive when customer demand expands. Thus customers are the ultimate resource on which companies depend. This is similar to the school system, where students are the customers whom the school depends for survival. Effective services must be provided through resource availability and utilization for students' retention, effective instructional delivery and positive outcomes. On this premise, the purpose of RDT is presenting a guide on how to design and manage organizations that are externally constrained. This is based on the basic assumption that an organization, or more precisely a manager, tries to ensure the organizational survival which is determined by the organizational ability to acquire and maintain resources. Theorists of RDT based their argument on the following tenet and notions that organizations depend on resources. These resources ultimately originate from an organization's external environment. In essence, RDT has been adopted by the present study because it shares connection with the study. The present study borders on finding out the availability and utilization of educational facilities and their significance on student performance; likewise, this theory sees the availability and utilization of facilities as the key to organizational success. Achievement of goals, survival of any organization including the school and workers' performance, is based upon their ability to use various facilities such as the classroom instructional facilities, library facilities and among others.

Also, that access and control over facilities is a basis of organizational power and functionality. This means that availability and utilization of facilities in the school organization will improve teacher performance and likewise impact on the quality of teaching-learning and promote students' academic achievements as well. They are the key to functionality and success in the school. Moreover, the RDT pays more attention to availability and utilization of resources in the school organization for customers (students) satisfaction without giving detailed preferences on teacher job performance. This has justified the need and warranted the second Two-Factor Theory by Frederick Herzberg of 1957 to cover the areas of teacher job performance.

Statement of the Problem

The problem of availability and utilization of educational facilities in connection with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State has become worrisome for the researcher, principals, teachers and other stakeholders in the state. A cursory look at the development of secondary schools in the state has shown that there are yet evidence of lapses in majority of the teachers' job performances and work. This seems to have negative consequences on secondary school students' academic performance in both internal and external examinations.

The researcher observes that the problem of availability and utilization of facilities as regards classroom instructional facilities, library facilities, laboratory facilities, recreational facilities, technology facilities, staff rooms and administrative facilities and transportation facilities existing in the secondary schools in River State, which could correlate with students' academic performance seem to be questionable. The researcher's observation shows that many of the teachers in secondary schools in Rivers State, whether rural or urban secondary schools, are still teaching with less or no facilities which hinders secondary school students' academic performance. With this devastating state, teachers have difficulties in performing their tasks and functions relating to secondary school students' academic performance. This situation has constituted a big challenge for students' academic performance in the state. The only way secondary schools within the state can continue to achieve their goals is when educational facilities are accessible, sufficiently available and easily utilized by teachers and students. This is so because teachers are important machineries that impact greatly on students' academic performance. Without their effectiveness, students' academic progress and the promotion of quality education system might become a difficult task. The problem concerning availability and utilization of educational facilities as correlates of secondary school students' academic performance therefore stands as the gap which must be filled in order to bridge the knowledge gap and for quality education system to be harnessed in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to examine educational facilities availability and utilization as correlates of secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives were to:

1. determine the extent to which availability of classroom instructional facilities correlates with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria.
2. determine the extent to which utilization of classroom instructional facilities correlates with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. To what extent does availability of classroom instructional facilities correlate with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria?
2. To what extent does utilization of classroom instructional facilities correlate with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 levels of significance.

H0₁: There is no significant correlation between availability of classroom instructional facilities and secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria.

H0₂: There is no significant correlation between utilization of classroom instructional facilities and secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

This study applied a correlational research design. The population of the study comprised all the 8,452 teachers in 268 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Source: Statistics Department of Rivers State Ministry of Education (2025). A sample size 382 teachers representing 4.51% was drawn from a total population of 8,452 teachers using Taro Yamane minimum formula. Stratified random sampling technique was used to draw the respondents. This study made use of three different sets of instruments for the purpose of gathering data. The research instruments included a Checklist titled: "Educational Facilities Availability Checklist (EFAC)" and questionnaire titled: "Utilization of Educational Facilities Questionnaire (UEFQ) and Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (SAPQ)". The instruments comprised two sections, A and B. Section A covered information on the demographic characteristics while Section B was designed to generate relevant information based on the variables of the study. The modified four-point Likert-type scale of Very High Extent (VHE) = 4 points, High Extent (HE) = 3 points, Low Extent (LE) = 2 points and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1 point will be adopted to elicit responses from the respondents. The initial draft of the instruments was given to the researcher's supervisors and two experts in Measurement and Evaluation, and Guidance and Counselling in the Faculty of Education for critical study and improvements. They were presented with the topic of the study as well as the objectives of the study for critical analysis. Their comments, criticisms and observations were incorporated to improve the quality of the final draft of the instrument to ensure both face and content validities before the instruments were administered to the respondents. The internal consistency was determined using Cronbach Alpha Statistics. Simple regression was used to answer research questions 1 – 2. While t-test associated with simple regression was used to test the null hypotheses 1 – 2 at 0.05 level of significance.

Coefficient Determination (R-squared)

76 – 100%
51 – 75%
26 – 50%
0 – 25%

Interpretations

Very High
High
Moderate
Low

RESULTS

Answer to Research Questions

Research Question 1: *To what extent does availability of classroom instructional facilities correlate with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Simple Regression on the Relationship between availability of classroom instructional facilities correlate with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.307 ^a	.094	.092	.26313

a. Predictors: (Constant), Classroom Instructional Facilities

Table 1 show the results of a linear regression carried out to investigate the extent availability of classroom instructional facilities correlate with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.30$), which showed that to a moderate extent, availability of classroom instructional facilities correlate with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria. The coefficient of determination (R-squared) associated with the linear regression (R) of 0.30 was 0.094. This coefficient of determination (R-squared) indicates that, availability of classroom instructional facilities accounted for 9.4% of secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria. This is an indication that other factors affect availability of classroom instructional facilities correlate with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria accounted for 90.6%. Therefore, to a moderate extent, availability of classroom instructional facilities correlates with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does utilization of classroom instructional facilities correlate with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Simple Regression on the Relationship between utilization of classroom instructional facilities correlate with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.788 ^a	.621	.620	.17016

a. Predictors: (Constant), Utilization of classroom instructional facilities

Table 2 show the results of a linear regression carried out to investigate the extent utilization of classroom instructional facilities correlate with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.78$), which showed that to a very high extent, utilization of classroom instructional facilities correlate with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria. The coefficient of determination (R-squared) associated with the linear regression (R) of 0.78 was 0.621. This coefficient of determination (R-squared) indicates that, utilization of classroom instructional facilities accounted for 62.1% of secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria. This is an indication that other factors affect utilization of classroom instructional facilities correlate with secondary school students' academic performance in

Rivers State, Nigeria accounted for 37.9%. Therefore, to a very high extent, utilization of classroom instructional facilities correlates with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Result of Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant correlation between availability of classroom instructional facilities and secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 3: t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Relationship between availability of classroom instructional facilities and secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria

Table 3: t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Relationship between availability of classroom instructional facilities and secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.412	.121		11.656	.000
	Classroom Instructional Facilities	.498	.080	.307	6.204	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Students' Academic Performance

Table 3 show the results of simple regression carried out to investigate whether there is a significant correlation between availability of classroom instructional facilities and secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.30$), but availability of classroom instructional facilities model contributed significantly to the model with $\beta = 0.49$ and the

significant value of 0.00 was less than $p = 0.05$, which show that to a significant relationship between availability of classroom instructional facilities and secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria. The t-test value 6.204 associated with linear regression was statistically significant at 0.000 when subjected to 0.05 alpha level of significance. By implication, the null hypothesis was rejected and we accept the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant correlation between availability of classroom instructional facilities and secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant correlation between utilization of classroom instructional facilities and secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 4: t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Relationship between availability of classroom instructional facilities and secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.813	.055		14.679	.000
	Utilization of classroom instructional facilities	.587	.024	.788	24.633	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Students' Academic Performance

Table 4 show the results of simple regression carried out to investigate whether there is a significant correlation between utilization of classroom instructional facilities and secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.78$), but utilization of classroom instructional facilities model contributed significantly to the model with $\beta = 0.58$ and the significant value of 0.00 was less than $p = 0.05$, which show that to a significant relationship between utilization of classroom instructional facilities and secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria. The t-test value 24.633 associated with linear regression was statistically significant at 0.000 when subjected to 0.05 alpha level of significance. By implication, the null hypothesis was rejected and we accept the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant correlation between utilization of classroom instructional facilities and secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The extent availability of classroom instructional facilities correlate with secondary school students' academic performance.

The findings from research question one showed that to a moderate extent, availability of classroom instructional facilities correlate with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria. This means that to a moderate extent whiteboards/chalkboards, projectors, interactive smart boards, computers or laptops, internet access/ wi-fi, audio-visual equipment, laboratory equipment, textbooks and reference books, charts and posters, classroom desks and chairs, teacher's desk and chair, notice boards, learning management systems, classroom libraries or book corners, printers and photocopiers, mathematical instruments, educational software and apps, language labs, air conditioning or fans and scanners correlate with secondary school students' academic performance. This finding is in agreement with Adeboye and Akinbile (2021) who found that classroom environment factors such as air quality, lighting, and noise levels were strongly associated with students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Nigeria. The study indicated that students performed better in classrooms with appropriate environmental conditions. Well-equipped classrooms can improve teacher effectiveness. When teachers have access to a variety of instructional materials and resources, they are more likely to implement innovative teaching strategies that can address the needs of diverse learners. This, in turn, impacts students' academic performance positively. The research conducted by Oduro-Awuku et al. (2022) showed a positive correlation between teachers' access to instructional facilities and their teaching performance. Teachers who had access to adequate resources were able to deliver lessons more effectively, leading to improved student outcomes. In today's digital age, the integration of technology in classrooms can significantly improve academic performance, particularly in subjects like Mathematics, Science, and Languages. The internet, educational software, and digital learning platforms help students access a wide range of information and learning materials.

The extent utilization of classroom instructional facilities correlate with secondary school students' academic performance

The findings from research question two showed that to a very high extent, utilization of classroom instructional facilities correlate with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria. This means that to a very high extent, utilization of whiteboards/chalkboards improves students' understanding, utilization of projectors like smart boards make lessons more engaging, utilization of interactive smart boards increase student participation, boosting academic outcomes, utilization of computers or laptops foster digital literacy as well as support a wide range of learning styles, utilization of internet access/wi-fi expand students' knowledge of research work, utilization of laboratory equipment enhances understanding of scientific concepts through application, improving science performance, utilization of textbooks and reference books positively influence academic performance, utilization of charts and posters provide constant visual reminders, aiding students' retention, utilization of classroom desks and chairs provide comfort to the students, reduces distractions, utilization of teachers' desk and

chair promote conducive learning environment, utilization of noticeboards keep students informed, aiding their academic performance, utilization of learning management systems enhance both academic and administrative performance, utilization of classroom libraries or book corners encourage independent learning and critical thinking and utilization of printers and photocopiers promote balance learning environment for students. This finding is in agreement with Alabi and Olanrewaju (2020) who examined the impact of digital learning tools on students' academic performance in Nigerian secondary schools. The study concluded that the integration of ICT tools in classrooms significantly improved students' academic achievements, especially in subjects that required problem-solving skills. Classroom instructional facilities are undeniably essential to fostering an environment where students can excel academically. From the use of modern technology and visual aids to the physical design of the classroom, these facilities contribute to students' engagement, motivation, understanding, and overall performance. Empirical studies consistently show that access to these resources positively influences academic outcomes, enhancing both teacher performance and student achievements.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings from this study, it was concluded that to a very high extent, availability and utilization of classroom instructional facilities and library facilities correlate with secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria. There is a significant correlation between availability and utilization of classroom instructional facilities, library facilities and secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers state, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study offered the following recommendations for implementation:

1. Government should create enabling policies and incentives that encourage private sector investment in education infrastructure, ensuring sustainable support for instructional facility development and effective monitoring mechanisms to guarantee quality and usage.
2. Stakeholders, including school boards and education quality assurance agencies, should establish a monitoring and evaluation framework to ensure that instructional facilities provided are being consistently and properly used.

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